

Charming while strangely funny

Analogica Tako

September 29, 2024

[BOOK REVIEW]

Following is a combined review of two reviewers, nicknamed Analogica [1] and Tako [2], on Amazon for [Wild Wise Weird](#) (formerly, *The Kingfisher Story Collection*) [3].

Analogica:

This collection of fables – all about a bird! – are charming and warm, filled with wit and humor and thoughtful lessons. And of Vietnamese origin!

A wonderful book.

 Analogica

Charming!

Reviewed in the United States on September 21, 2024

This collection of fables - all about a bird! - are charming and warm, filled with wit and humor and thoughtful lessons. And of Vietnamese origin! A wonderful book.

Helpful

Report

Screenshot. A Review of “Wild Wise Weird” by Analogica. Reviewed in the United States on September 21, 2024 [1].

Tako:

The style feels traditional and modern at the same time.

The stories seem casual and playful yet the implications may be quite serious.

The tone is respectful, but you may guess that the experiences in the stories came from not-so-friendly social contexts.

Overall, the book feels like a strange mixture of... life. Raw yet filtered.

Tako

★★★★★ Verified Purchase

Strangely funny

Reviewed in the United States on May 1, 2023

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The tone is respectful, but you may guess that the experiences in the stories came from not-so-friendly social contexts.

Overall, the book feels like a strange mixture of... life. Raw yet filtered.

It is funny not because it is strange. It is funny in a strange way.

Screenshot. A Review of “The Kingfisher Story Collection” by Tako. Reviewed in the United States on May 1, 2023 [2].

It is funny not because it is strange. It is funny in a strange way.

References

[1] Analogica (2024). Charming!. <https://www.amazon.com/gp/customer-reviews/R2K5G7PKXF85ZI/>

[2] Tako (2023). Strangely funny. <https://www.amazon.com/gp/customer-reviews/>

[R2RR5DOS6JAQCH/](#)

[3] Vuong QH. (2024). *Wild Wise Weird*. <https://www.amazon.com/dp/B0BG2NNHY6>

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